

Motivational Skills of Teachers and Academic Performance of Grade Five Students in the New Normal

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Abstract. The general purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between teachers' motivational skills and the academic performance of Grade Five students in the new normal. A quasi-experimental research design was employed, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. This design is suitable when the researcher has access to only one group for experimentation (Vockel, 1983). The researcher chose this design because the study subjects were an intact group of learners. The study was conducted at Almendras Elementary School in the Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects consisted of 90 Grade Five students, with 47 students in section A serving as the control group and 43 students in section B serving as the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous, with both groups having identical grades. Non-random assignment was used, involving all students from both sections A and B as study subjects. The findings of the study revealed that teachers' motivational skills significantly increased the academic performance of Grade Five students in the new normal. Additionally, there was a notable difference in the post-test scores between the control and experimental groups

KEY WORDS

1. Motivation. 2. Performance.

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1. Introduction

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic dramatically altered various aspects of human life, including the socio-economic, psychological, and emotional domains. Among the most affected sectors was education, which faced unprecedented challenges as students and teachers were forced to adapt to new learning modalities. This shift highlighted the critical role of teachers' motivation in ensuring students' academic success. Teachers' motivation, a key factor in student performance, became even more crucial as many elementary students lost interest in their academic workload, feeling detached and unmotivated due to the lack of interaction with peers and educators (Rawahhi et al., 2019). The pandemic-induced transition to online learning exacerbated student motivation and performance issues. Students often felt isolated and disconnected, leading to declining enthusiasm and engagement with academic tasks. The lack of a supportive academic environment and insufficient knowledge and guidance contributed to poor academic outcomes. This situation highlighted the urgent need for effective motivational strategies from teachers to enhance students' self-efficacy and educational outcomes

(Brook et al., 2019). Teacher motivation is pivotal in the education system, directly influencing student performance. Motivated teachers are likelier to engage students effectively, creating a conducive learning environment that fosters academic achievement. Studies have shown that teachers' motivational skills can significantly improve students' educational outcomes and self-efficacy, which are essential for their academic success (Uyulgan Akkuzu, 2020). In terms of academic achievement, motivation positively impacts each student's performance uniquely. Poor academic performance, characterized by high failure rates, leads to increased attrition, decreased graduation rates, and higher educational costs (Malasaga et al., 2019). Globally, the lack of student motivation is evident, as seen in Oman, where academic success rates among public school students vary significantly. Reports indicate low performance in grades 5 and 6, suggesting a need for enhanced motivational strategies to boost academic achievements, particularly in online learning environments (Ministry of Education, 2019). The significance of teacher motivation extends beyond individual countries, affecting global education systems. For instance, Filipino learners benefit from teacher motivation, which helps them stay connected and engaged with their peers and educators. However, Filipino teachers, particularly those in the Department of Education, face challenges such as high workloads and inadequate compensation, which diminish their motivation and hinder professional development (Albert, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic further strained these teachers, highlighting the need for supportive measures to maintain their motivation and, consequently, their students' academic performance. In the Philippines, the educational system struggles with issues like overworking teachers and stagnant salaries. These challenges lead to a decrease in teachers' motivation, impacting their ability to inspire and educate effectively. Additionally, students' mental health has

suffered due to the pandemic, making teacher motivation even more critical to boosting students' confidence and academic performance in the new normal of online learning (Lopez Irene, 2019). Despite the recognized importance of teacher motivation, specific studies addressing this issue in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic remain limited. For example, in the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly at Almendras Elementary School, no studies have been conducted to examine teachers' motivational skills and their impact on learners' academic performance during the pandemic. This gap in research underscores the need to explore how teachers' motivational strategies can be improved to enhance student outcomes in the new normal. The existing literature emphasizes the critical role of teacher motivation in shaping student academic performance. Various studies highlight the positive correlation between teachers' motivational skills and students' educational outcomes. For instance, Abbas Khurshid (2019) found that motivational approaches can inspire interest and excitement among students, significantly influencing their academic performance. Similarly, Lawrence Hanitha (2019) demonstrated a positive relationship between teachers' motivational strategies and the academic success of higher secondary learners. Motivational skills are crucial for creating a dynamic and engaging classroom environment where students are eager to learn and participate actively. These skills help students develop a growth mindset and resilience, essential for overcoming academic challenges (Dweck, 2020). Effective motivational strategies, such as providing constructive feedback and creating a positive learning atmosphere, are vital for fostering student engagement and success (Obot et al., 2019). In conclusion, the literature underscores the pivotal role of teachers' motivational skills in enhancing students' academic performance. By fostering a supportive and engaging learning environment, teachers can inspire stu-

dents to achieve their full potential. This study aims to fill the research gap by investigating the impact of teachers' motivational skills on the academic performance of Grade 5 students in the new normal, with a focus on Almendras Elementary School. The findings will provide valuable insights for educational stakeholders to implement effective motivational strategies, ultimately improving student outcomes in the challenging landscape of post-pandemic education.

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic had dramatically affected the socio-economic, psychological, and emotional aspects of humans. It also affects the education system, where students and teachers were forced to adapt to another learning modality. On this modality, the call for teacher's motivation is increased. Teachers' motivation was one of the critical factors why students perform well in school. However, many elementary students had lost their desire to do their academic workload and found themselves detached from the group because of the lack of motivation, which leads to the decline of their interest and enthusiasm in performing their tasks (Rawahhi et al., 2019). Students may feel separated and bored because they are not linked with their classmates and constitute the feeling of being left-behind. The lack of knowledge towards academic background may also contribute to the decrease of student's performance. The dismal performance among elementary students may increase because of the lack of motivation from their teachers, parents, and classmates, especially during the surge of the COVID-19 pandemic. Several studies had reiterated that higher motivational skills of teachers can envisage the students' educational outcomes and achievement and improve their self-efficacy (Brook et.al, 2019). The concept of motivation was one of the essential factors in determining the success and failure of a student. A very important concept for both teachers and students in distinguishing the root cause of fail-

ure and success in the entire education system (Uyulgan Akkuzu, 2020). A motivated teacher will make more efforts in the classroom to pass on adequate information to his students in order to influence the learner's behavior in the most preferable and positive way. In terms of academic achievement, motivation has been found to favorably influence each student's academic performance in a unique way. Poor academic performance or high failure rates can lead to unacceptable levels of attrition, decreased graduate throughout, and increased educational costs (Malasaga et.al, 2019). On a global scale, a lack of motivation among students in Oman is evident. Statistics showed differences in the academic success rates of public-school students in Su-mail, Oman ranging from 62 percent to 75 percent. The differences are varied among the learners in grade 5 and grade 6. Additionally, a report from the Ministry of Education shows that students in 5th and 6th grade have low academic performance in their class (Ministry of Education, 2019). The report suggests that teachers and schools should utilize various techniques to motivate students to achieve their academic goals and increase their academic performance, especially when online learning is the dominant norm of education today. Similarly, the essence of teacher's motivation encourages Filipino learners to continue realizing their goals and accomplish their tasks. Filipino learners were motivated when connected with their classmates and teachers; by simply giving the students some updates and a positive word to lighten up their day. However, teachers in the Philippines, especially those in the Department of Education, were overworking based on the teaching hours and high student-teacher ratio. Sometimes, because of the bunch of reports, lesson plans, and other paperwork that a teacher needs to finish, they cannot give enough time to teach their students. These situations lead to a decrease in teacher's motivation and a reduction in interest in seeking professional develop-

ment (Albert, 2020). Further, salaries were stagnant for public school teachers, and some were under-paid. Their salary was not enough to pay their bills and other liabilities; others choose to have loans to satisfy their needs (Lopez Irene, 2019). If this situation continues to persist, many teachers will lose their interest in teaching, and if so, it will have a massive impact on the entire education system. Also, the devastating impact brought by the COVID-19 pandemic has intensified the situation. Some students had been a victim of stress and depression; thus, teachers' motivation was needed to boost the student's confidence amidst online learning. In the Division of Davao del Sur, particularly in Almendras Elementary School, no study has been conducted to look for teachers' motivational skills and how it affects the learners' academic performance during this pandemic. Thus, the researcher finds it appropriate and timely to conduct this study to propose a plan of action on how teachers in ALES further improve their motivational skills, especially in the new normal.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—

1.1.1. *Academic Performance*—Academic performance, an outcome of education, gauges how well students, teachers, or institutions meet educational goals. Factors like teaching effectiveness, learning materials, and school facilities significantly influence academic performance (Malasaga et al., 2019; Carmen, 2019). Assessments, commonly exams or continuous evaluations, measure this performance, although methods vary (Okon, 2020).

Excellence in academic performance includes achievements in both curricular and extracurricular activities such as sports, communication skills, punctuality, and the arts. This holistic measure is crucial as job market competitiveness heightens, drawing interest from parents, legislators, and education departments (Singh, Singh, Malik, 2019). GPA is often used as an indicator of academic success, reflecting cumulative and final achievements (The Higher

Education Academy, 2020).

The academic success of students is pivotal for producing quality graduates who contribute to socioeconomic development (Term Paper, 2021). Studies reveal that factors like the availability of qualified teachers and educational resources, as well as teachers' experience, significantly impact student performance (Mosha, 2020; Taylor, 2019). Effective learning environments, supported by adequate government funding, are essential (Singh, Singh, Malik, 2019).

1.1.2. *Motivation and Academic Performance*—Motivation is essential for learning, fostering student engagement and effective learning outcomes. It consists of intrinsic factors, driven by personal satisfaction, and extrinsic factors, driven by external rewards (Palmer, 2020; Wang, 2020). Motivated students show higher engagement and persistence, leading to better academic performance (Dai, 2020; Beck, 2021).

Studies indicate a significant correlation between motivation and academic performance (Abu Bakar, 2019). For instance, a study among Malaysian university students found that self-concept and achievement motivation positively affect academic performance (Alsmadi, 2020). Similar results were observed among undergraduates at UniSZA, where motivation strongly influenced GPA (Mahyuddin, 2019).

Teachers' motivational skills, along with school administrators' support and parental involvement, enhance student motivation, confidence, and academic success (Tobgay, 2021; Lawrence Hanitha, 2019). Effective motivational strategies create a positive learning environment and encourage student participation (Jones, 2018; Dweck, 2020). These strategies are particularly crucial in adapting to the new normal in education (Obot et al., 2019).

Teacher motivation is critical, as motivated teachers inspire students, fostering a conducive learning atmosphere (McFerren, 2019). Re-

search underscores the importance of teachers' motivational skills in shaping students' academic outcomes, highlighting the need for supportive and enthusiastic teaching practices (Koomen, 2017).

By summarizing and merging related findings, this literature review highlights the integral role of motivational skills and various educational factors in enhancing academic performance.

1.2. Synthesis—The literature review presented above provides an overview of the perspectives and viewpoints of various authors regarding the significance of motivational skills of teacher's that can lead to improved students, academic performance. While some authors share similar ideas, there are also contrasting statements. These statements will serve as a guide for the researcher in conducting her own study, forming conclusions, and making recommendations. Additionally, the literature review will serve as a frame-work for the researcher to follow throughout the research process. It will also serve as a reference for the researcher to support and justify any findings that arise from the statistical analysis and interpretation.

1.3. Theoretical/ Conceptual Framework—This study was anchored on the Theory of Needs of Abraham Maslow and Self-Determination Theory. According to some writers, motivation was linked to daily needs and the desire to perform better. Maslow's (1943) need-based theory of motivation proposes that a person has five basic needs: physiological, security, affiliation, esteem, and self-actualization. Pay, food, shelter, clothing, and comfortable working conditions were examples of physiological needs. Security needs include safety, fair treatment, protection from threats, and job security. Affiliation needs had the desire to be loved, accepted, and a part of a group, whereas esteem needs include the desire for recognition, respect, achievement, autonomy, and independence. Subsequently, the highest

level of Maslow's need theory includes self-actualization needs, which must realize one's full potential or self-development; the author refers to this as the pinnacle of one's calling. Once a condition is met, it was no longer a need, according to Maslow. It no longer motivates employee behavior, and they were motivated by a need at the next level up the hierarchy. As a result, motivation was directly related to an individual's needs, and as those needs are met, the level of motivation decreases or diminishes over time. Self-determination theory, on the one hand, focuses on the idea of the person's ability to make decisions and manage their own life. This ability is critical to one's mental health and well-being. People who have self-determination believe they have control over their choices and lives. It also influences motivation; people are more motivated to act when they believe that there is a positive outcome to their actions (Cherry, 2021). This theory was developed Edward Deci and Ryan framework for studying the humans' personality and their motivation. SDT articulates the roles of intrinsic and types of extrinsic motivation in cognitive and social development and individual differences. Perhaps more importantly, SDT recommendations consider how social and cultural factors influence people's sense of well-being and performance quality (CSDT, 2021). Thus, these two theories best explain why teachers had low or high motivational skills. If all the needs and desires of teachers are satisfied, their level of motivational skills will increase. If it happens, students will be motivated to do their part as a student because they are influenced and encouraged by their teachers to do their best. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of this experimental research. The action initiated was the use of teacher's motivational skills and it hopefully affects the academic performance of Grade five students in the new normal. It was hoped that through the use of this approach, the academic performance of the students will be

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study

increased.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The general purpose of this study was to look into the relationship between the motivational skills of teachers and the academic performance of Grade 5 students in the new normal. Specifically, this research study aims to answer the following research objectives.

- (1) What was the pretest score of Grade 5 students both controlled and experimental groups before the implementation of teacher’s motivational skills?
- (2) What was the post-test of Grade 5 students both controlled and experimental groups after the implementation of teacher’s motivational skills?
- (3) Is there a significant difference of the academic performance of Grade five students between controlled and experimental groups after the implementation of teacher’s motivational skills?
- (4) What was the magnitude effect of teacher’s motivational skills on the academic performance of Grade five students in the new normal?

1.5. Null Hypothesis—The Null Hypothesis in this study was tested at 0.05 level of significance. HO1. The teachers’ motivational skills had no significant relationship in the academic performance of Grade five students in the new normal. HO2. Teachers’ motivational skills had no magnitude effect on the academic performance of Grade five students in the new normal.

1.6. Significance of the Study—This study was of importance to the teachers of Almendras

Elementary School and the Division of Davao del Sur and will benefited the following:

DepEd Officials. The result of this study revealed the level of motivational skills of teachers and how it affects the academic performance of students in the new normal. Further, this study served as the basis for DepEd Officials to initiate various seminars and relevant training across many disciplines as to how teachers boost their motivational skills, especially in this challenging time, to function effectively to re-

spond to the various call of global demands.

School Administrators. The findings of this study were beneficial to the school head of Almendras Elementary School. The school head can utilize the vital information from this research study to improve the teachers' various skills and competence that will directly affect students' academic performance. As instructional leaders, school heads are tasked to implement different instructions to promote teachers' pedagogy in realizing the learning institutions' goals, missions, and visions.

Teachers. The findings of this research study were helpful to teachers of ALES as to what strategies they will employ in motivating their learners, especially during this pandemic, where students were vulnerable to many stresses. As teachers simple motivation was enough to encourage students to do their academic responsibilities and perform better.

Future Researchers. The findings of this study encouraged them to conduct similar stud-

ies in other areas. This study served as an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study.

Definition of Terms The following terms were defined operationally for a comprehensive and unified understanding of the readers.

Motivational Skills. As used in this study, motivational skills refer to the actions and strategies of teachers in eliciting desired behaviors from students.

Grade 5 Students. It refers to the students enrolled in the ninth level of the education ladder as stipulated in the K-12 Curriculum of the Department of Education. Specifically, these students are the grade 5 students enrolled in Almendras Elementary School.

Academic Performance. As used in this study, it refers to the result or outcomes exerted by the students in every grading period, which indicates the extent to which a student has attained specific goals.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Locale and Sample—This study was conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 90 grade five students – 47 were from section A were the controlled group and 43 were from section B which were the ex-

perimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

Distribuiion of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	A	47
2	B	43
	Total	90

2.2. *Data Source and Analysis*—This researcher had access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the academic performance of grade five students in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of effect of motivational skills of teachers on the academic skills of grade five students in the new normal. This study utilized the new normal learning modality. It was a blended learning where the teacher gave module at the same met the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher had met the learners online for a follow up session of what

had been printed in the module. The pre- and post-performance test consist of a 45 –item test that eventually de-termined the reading skills of the research subjects. The pretest was administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the academic per-formance of grade five students in the new-normal. On the other hand, posttest was ad-ministered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the letter sound recognition skills of the pre-school learners, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system.

2.3. *Data Gathering and Processing*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking permission that this research study be conducted to the Schools Division Superintendent. 1. Permission to Conduct Study. While letters seeking permission were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts, preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Almen-

dras Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered post-test to both sections. Scores of the subjects submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills, and understandings, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings, and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presented the discussion of the problems in this study. They were discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relation-ship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the pre-school learners. The controlled group got the mean of 16.22 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 17.03 or Beginning.

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs to Beginning level. This finding was congruent to the statement of Suhag (2020) who states that motivation was an essential element in the process of learning and holds significant significance in facilitating student engagement in academic pursuits. Motivation can be defined as a state or condition that provides impetus to behavior, guiding and maintaining its momentum. This encompasses objectives and activities that necessitate motivation for movement and action. Sustained operation of action necessitates both exertion and perseverance. Motivation encompasses a collec-

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	47	32.75	72.77	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	43	33.60	74.66	Beginning

tion of interconnected beliefs, perceptions, values, information, and actions. Motivation plays a significant role in driving various behaviors, and it is crucial to comprehend its significance within an educational context. Motivation was an emotional sensation that emerges from an individual’s desires and requirements. Individuals were motivated to perform because of a

constant process of demands and pleasure. It was the process of encouraging a person to use their most outstanding qualities to attain specific goals. Motivational approaches can inspire interest and excitement and govern individual behavior to accomplish various tasks to achieve specific goals (Abbas Khurshid, 2019).

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	47	32.75	72.77	Beginning
Post-test	47	36.63	81.4	Developing
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	43	33.60	74.66	Beginning
Post-test	43	38.83	86.28	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 were the post-test scores of grades five students. The controlled group got the mean of 36.63 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 38.83 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group had a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 5.23 from a mean rating of 33.60 to 38.83. This means that the experimental group had a far better performance than the controlled

group. This finding was congruent to the idea of Lawrecne Hanitha (2019) who cited that that there was a significant positive relationship between the motivational strategy of teachers and academic success of higher secondary learners. The result indicated that motivational skills of teachers as used in classroom instructions have notable effect to the academic performance of students. Hence, teachers’ motivational skills and strategy were critical factors in improving the students’ self-motivation and improve the

performance of the learners in school. Motivation was recognized as one of the fundamental components that significantly impact students' learning and is viewed as extremely important in supporting good education. Because the suc-

cess of students' learning depends on teachers' use of motivational skills, teachers' excellent and practical use of motivational skills is critical to winning in the teaching-learning process (Tobgay, 2021).

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	37	-5.18	.0413	Significant

Table 3 showed the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.18 with a p-value of .0413 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade nine students. This implies that motivational skills of teachers in teaching grade nine students have contributed to the effectiveness in academic performance which is revealed by the scores of the grade nine students. This finding was in line with the statement of Koomen (2017) who said that teachers who possess strong motivational skills have the power to inspire their stu-

dents, cultivate a positive learning environment, and enhance overall academic outcomes. By incorporating elements of encouragement, support, and enthusiasm in their teaching practices, teachers can effectively motivate students to reach their full potential. Motivational skills refer to the ability of a teacher to inspire and encourage students to strive for success. When teachers possess strong motivational skills, they can create a positive and dynamic classroom atmosphere where students are eager to learn and participate actively. Motivation was a key factor in student achievement, with motivated students showing higher levels of engagement, persistence, and academic success (Jones, 2018).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Pre-kindergarten learners

N	t-value	η^2	Descriptive Value	Decision
40	-4.21	0.421	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of motivational skills of teachers on the academic performance of grade five students in the new normal. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.421 which signifies a large effect. This implies that teachers should look for a strategy in developing motivational skills that can affect the academic performance of grade five students in the new normal. Motivational skills are an essential component of effective teaching, impacting not only academic

outcomes but also the overall development of students. Teachers who master motivational techniques can inspire and engage students, creating a dynamic and productive learning environment. Motivational skills helped students develop a growth mindset and resilience in the face of challenges. When teachers provided constructive feedback, support, and encouragement, students learn to view setbacks as opportunities for growth and learning. Fostering a growth

mindset in students, where they believe that their abilities can be developed through dedication and hard work (Dweck, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displayed the summary of the discussions and implications drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the effect of motivational skills of teachers on the academic performance of grade five students in new normal. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which was a non-equivalent control group pretest-post-test design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Almendras Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 90 grade five students – 47 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 43 were from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B had identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. This study revealed that the motivational skills of teachers has increased the academic performance of grade five students in new normal. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions were drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade five students in both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group was at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group was at the Approach-

ing Proficiency level.

4.2. Limitations and Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It was recommended that teachers teaching grade five students should use effective motivational skills as a strategy that would further develop the academic performance of grade five students in the new normal. Motivational skills are essential for teachers to create an engaging and productive learning environment. These skills not only enhance students' academic performance but also foster a positive attitude towards learning. The school heads should promote to enhance motivational skills as a strategy that would enhance the academic performance of grade five students in new normal as it is revealed in the study that it is effective especially in challenging times that mental fortitude needed to overcome obstacles and achieve their academic goals. A school policy about the utilization of motivational strategy can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demo teach during LAC session using motivational strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on motivational skills of teachers in teaching be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

4.3. Conclusions and Reflections—According to the findings, kids who were taught by teachers who employed motivating tactics made considerable progress in their academic performance. The experimental group's post-test scores were close to proficiency, while the control group's levels approached the Devel-

oping level. The results highlight how crucial motivating techniques are for raising student achievement and attitudes toward learning. As a result, the study suggests that educators receive training in these techniques, that school administrators embrace motivational techniques, that supportive policies be created, and that additional research be done to investigate other facets of education. Putting these suggestions into practice can improve students' academic development and well-being especially considering the new normal.

5. References

- Abocejo, F. T. (2022). The informal reading inventory (phil-iri) program: An analysis of budapest international research and critics in linguistics and education (birle) journal, approach. *Budapest International Research and Critics in Linguistics and Education (BirLE) Journal*.
- Ashdown, J., & Simic, O. (2020). Is early literacy intervention effective for english language learners? evidence from reading recovery. *Literacy Teaching and Learning*, 5, 27–42.
- Bettinger, E. P., & Long, B. T. (2019). Addressing the needs of under-prepared students in higher education: Does college remediation work? *Journal of Human Resources*, 44, 736–771.
- Boltron, M. T., & Ramos, A. L. (2021). Improving beginning reading literacy through marungko.
- Borgonovi, F., Ikeda, M., & Park, S. (2021). Does investing in after-school classes pay off? *PISA in Focus*, 3, 1–4.
- Borman, G. (2021). Summers are for learning. *Principal*, 80(3), 26–29.
- Brothen, T., & Wambach, C. A. (2024). Refocusing developmental education. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 28(1), 16–22.
- Case, M. (2018). The impact of reading recovery on the reading achievement of first grade.
- Clay, M. M. (n.d.). *An observation survey of early literacy achievement*. Heinemann.
- Cosden, M., Morrison, G., Gutierrez, L., & Brown, M. (2024). The effects of homework programs and after-school activities on school success. *Theory Into Practice*, 43, 220–226.
- Dennis, D. (2023). Resilience of the community in the early phase of the covid-19 pandemic.
- Estrema, M. L., & Estrema, G. L. (2018). Factors affecting the reading comprehension of grade six.
- Field, J. (2020). *Lifelong learning and the new educational order*. Trentham Books.
- Gordon, E. W., Bridglall, B. L., & Meroe, A. S. (Eds.). (2017). *Supplementary education: The hidden curriculum of high academic achievement*. Rowman & Littlefield. <https://shorturl.at/bgAQ7>
- Jacob, B. A., & Lefgren, L. (2024). Remedial education and student achievement: A regression-discontinuity analysis. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 86, 226–244.
- Lavy, V., & Schlosser, A. (2024). *Targeted remedial education for under-performing teenagers: Costs and benefits*. National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Little, P., Wimer, C., & Weiss, H. B. (2018). After school programs in the 21st century: Their potential and what it takes to achieve it. *Issues and Opportunities in Out-of-School Time Evaluation*, 10, 1–12.
- Luftig, R. (2023). When a little bit means a lot: The effects of a short-term reading program on poor elementary schoolers. *Reading Research and Instruction*, 42(4), 1–13.
- Vera, D., & Santos. (2021). Resilience of the community in the early phase of the covid-19 pandemic.